

MY LIFE PHILOSOPHY OR WHERE DO YOU IMAGINE YOURSELF IN 10 YEARS?

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Annotation: This article is a creative, written in a more motivational spirit to benefit the youth. Everyone reading the article is aimed at strengthening your sense of confidence. Excerpts from the lives of famous people, useful advise, and various quotes are also mentioned.

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Until a person came into the world and chose exactly one profession the variety remains among the choices. Right? Still just now someone is a doctor when we are in school to be, someone to be a teacher, and someone else to be a military dreamed of being. Remember those times? As a person grows up, the circle of his dreams also expands and he begins to set great goals for himself. A moment return to your childhood and try to remember. In your 1st grade

How did you answer the question of who you want to become in the future? And now your current goals for that answer compare with. In what area are you currently studying, what are specialist will you become in the future? The most important is 5 years, 7 years come, at what point do you imagine yourself after 10 years do you? Shouldn't you start work on this goals one by one? People must keep the goals huge, like a mountain. After all, people with high self-confidence have always been among the first.

Want to get the results you want? In it:

1. First of all, believe in yourself, find strength in yourself;
2. Direct your inner energy to your planned activities;
3. Consult with experienced people;
4. The most important thing is to follow your dreams;

5. Work on yourself;
6. Be sure to spend time reading books that interest you! (Audio books are also very useful in this regard)
7. Do not give up easily (although your dreams are not beyond your strength and capabilities).
8. Do not pay attention to those who do not believe in your capabilities (do not stop so that they can see your success);
9. Do not let small reasons get in the way of your big goals;
10. Believe strongly in success;

Dale Carnegie says this: "One of the tragic things I know about human nature is that we all tend to procrastinate. Instead of enjoying the roses outside our window today, we dream of a magical rose garden on some abstract future horizon."

Have you heard about 18 successful people who overcame failure? Now I will give some examples of them.

1. Winston Churchill was "stuck" in the sixth grade. At first, no matter how hard he tried, he could not get any of the political positions he wanted. But later, thanks to his efforts, he managed to become the Prime Minister of Great Britain at the age of 62.

2. Thomas Edison was always told by his teachers that "you're stupid, you can't learn something" and he was also accused of mental retardation. But one day Thomas Edison became an incomparable inventor.

3. We have often seen Harland David Sanders on the KFC logo. At first, Harland David Sanders could not sell his chicks to anyone.

4. Steven Spielberg always dreamed of entering the South California Film University. However, Stephen, who created an 8-minute film at the age of 12, failed to enter this school despite three consecutive attempts. You yourself are aware of today's success of the seven-time Oscar-winning filmmaker.

5. Charlie Chaplin's actions were not liked by directors and filmmakers. Many have forgotten the names of filmmakers who despised him.

6. Marilyn Monroe is a legendary actress. His first contract with Columbia Pictures was cancelled. The producers told her that she did not have enough beauty and talent to become an actress. And eventually, she will become a bright star of Hollywood.

7. When Walt Disney was working at a newspaper, the editor fired him. The editor tells him that his imagination is not developed, that he cannot work anywhere with this ability, that only empty ideas come out of his head. After that, Disney wants to try himself in business by founding several companies. But no luck. Then he filmed the cartoon "Korgyz"

8. Joan Rowling an unnamed writer, suddenly went backwards: her family did not like her, and she divorced her husband. She was in debt, and she was supporting her only daughter with her pension money. Then the author wrote the first novel about Harry Potter, which became a bestseller in a short period of time. Now this work is among the best-selling books at the international level.

Paulo Coelho's work "The Alchemist" has this sentence: "Regardless of who are you and what you do, when you want something from your heart, you will achieve it, because such a desire is created in the HEART OF THE UNIVERSE. And this is yours it's your luck. You are lucky. Keep in mind: it is always clear what you want you need to know".